

CITY ALERT APPLICATION

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Abstract— The number of India’s population residing in cities is increasing rapidly. The Smart Cities Mission is a new initiative taken by the Government of India, for economic growth and to improve resident's life quality by creating smart opportunities for citizens. These Smart Solutions might involve increased use of technology as well as the active involvement of citizens. Our proposed system will serve as a medium to spread information about various needs and concerns to the citizens. It will be a Mobile application that will inform users about news and information regarding electricity, water supply, traffic, public transport and special alerts like new governmental schemes, according to their location. Admin will update data on a server and users will receive them as notifications.

Index Terms — Smart Cities Mission, Mobile

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian government has started the Smart Cities Mission [2], an initiative to realize the dream of transforming India to digital India [1]. As India is a developing country and most of its population resides in cities, issues of water, electricity and traffic jams as well as negative effects of these issues are very common. Smart solutions consisting of technology and active participation of residents can provide some help in resolving these issues. Thus we are proposing a mobile application which will alert users about all happenings in their city through notifications and allow them to take measures accordingly.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This chapter includes discussion on similar or related work done on this topic using different technologies or strategies. FlashAlertMessenger [3] allows the public to view local news and receive push notifications of emergency alerts available on Flash Alert Newswire. It is possible to use it as a standalone news viewer or to link it to Flash Alert Messenger account for receiving emergency alert push notifications from the schools, police agencies or organizations selected by the user. The application is available only in some cities of United States.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

City Alert Application is a mobile application [4] to enable user to receive notifications related to health, various governmental schemes, public transport, electricity, water and

other important and emergency news in the areas selected by the user. The application will consist of a website to allow different admins from different departments, to log in to the

System and post notification and alerts. This notification and alerts will be then pushed to the user’s mobile phone according to the selected area of preference. It will consist of one to one chat facility so that any user can inform admin about issues admin is unaware about, so that it can be posted to notify all the users.

The objectives of the proposed system are:

- Inform residents about concerns related to their location.
- Create awareness about new governmental schemes
- Save time by informing about traffic jams and roadblocks.
- Alert residents about special events in a city

Scope of project:

This application is useful to the android users. Governmental officials as well as general public and other residents of city can use the application. Data Flow diagram for City Alert Application is as follows which shows interfacing details of City Alert Application.

Figure: At level: 2 Data Flow Diagram

The flowchart for CityAlert Application is as follows in figure.

Figure: Flow of CityAlert Application

IV. MODULES

A) Admin:

Admin will be able to log into the system and update information related to their department to inform users about a issue. There will be multiple admins from various sectors such as BMC, MSEB ETC.

B) User:

Users will consist of residents living in a city. Users will be students, business man, government officials, non-profit organization workers, shop vendors and people of other professions residing in a city.

C) Database:

Database will serve following purpose:

- Storing the information updated by various admins
- Retrieving the stored information

D) City Alert Application:

City Alert application will act as a medium for notifying users about the various issues and concerns such as traffic, water supply, electricity etc.

E) Server:

Server will push the notification posted by the admin on City Alert website to the user's mobile phone.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The aim of City Alert Application is providing alerts and notifications to users to inform them about the current issues related to their locality as well as new schemes announced by the government. The Application will notify users of water and electricity issues in their area, news related to public transport, traffic jams and roadblocks and special alerts regarding governmental schemes.

In future, it is possible to add more fields for notifications and extend scope to the whole country.

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